

Synthesis of iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) complexes with new quadridentate N, O⁻ donor ligands

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The reaction between anthranilic acid and oxalyl chloride/malonyl chloride results in new quadridentate ligands, bis(2-carboxyphenyl)oxamide [CPOA]/bis(2-carboxyphenyl)malonamide [CPMA]. These ligands form 1 : 1 complexes of general formula, [Fe(L)(H₂O)₂]Cl, [M(L)] and [Zn(L)].2H₂O, where L = CPOA or CPMA, M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}.

The organic compounds containing amide group play important role in biology, as it constitutes the repeating unit of the polypeptide macromolecules. Further, they have attracted the attention of coordination chemists as they serve as models for metal-peptide interactions and to metalloenzymes¹. In the present paper, the preparation and characterization of two new ligands, bis(2-carboxyphenyl)oxamide [CPOA] and bis(2-carboxyphenyl)malonamide [CPMA] and their complexes with Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are described.

Results and Discussion

The Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes with CPOA and CPMA (Table 1) are stable and non-hygroscopic. The molar conductance values of all the complexes in DMF except those of Fe^{III} complexes at a concentration of 10⁻³ M are very low (5–13 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹), indicating their non-ionic nature². The conductance values of the Fe^{III} complexes of CPOA and CPMA (29.3 and 30.8 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, respectively) in DMF suggest that the complexes are 1 : 1 electrolytes. The analytical and molar conductance studies suggest that the general formulas of the complexes as FeL(H₂O)₂.Cl, ML and ZnL.2H₂O, where L = CPOA or CPMA; M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Compd	Decomp temp	Metal %		μ _{eff} B M
		Found	Calcd.	
[Fe(CPOA)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	420	11.93	(12.31)	2.16
[Fe(CPMA)(H ₂ O) ₂]Cl	430	11.72	(11.94)	2.28
[Co(CPOA)]	390	15.68	(15.32)	2.48
[Co(CPMA)]	390	14.52	(14.78)	2.46
[Ni(CPOA)]	415	14.96	(15.25)	Dia
[Ni(CPMA)]	440	14.56	(14.72)	Dia
[Cu(CPOA)]	420	16.04	(16.31)	1.87
[Cu(CPMA)]	450	15.94	(15.74)	1.85
[Zn(CPOA)].2H ₂ O	430	15.49	(15.29)	Dia
[Zn(CPMA)].2H ₂ O	450	15.26	(14.81)	Dia

The thermograms of Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} complexes of CPOA and CPMA exhibit endothermic peaks in the DSC curves in the temperature range 150–175° and 70–105°, respectively, and the percentage mass loss was found to correspond to two water molecules. The expulsion of water molecules in the high temperature range in the Fe^{III} complexes confirms that they are coordinated³. The loss of two water molecules in the low temperature region in the Zn^{II} complexes indicates that they are lattice-held³. The thermograms of the Fe^{III} complexes show second stage mass-loss curves at 420–560° with the corresponding exothermic peak in DSC⁴. The percentage loss was found to be slightly more than that required for the ligands indicating the loss of Cl⁻ ion also. The percentage of residue left 17.92 (17.55 calcd.) and 17.68 (17.03 calcd.) conform to the oxide, Fe₂O₃ in both the cases. Thermograms of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes exhibit single stage decomposition curve starting at 390, 415 and 420°, respectively, and becomes parallel to the temperature axis after 550°. No endothermic peaks attributable to loss of water or change in the physical state⁵ were observed. The exothermic peak at 390–550° confirms the loss of ligand moieties. The percentage mass loss and the residue left account respectively for the ligand and the metal oxide, Co₃O₄⁶, NiO⁷ and CuO⁸. The data confirm that formulas of the complexes as [M(CPOA)] and [M(CPMA)], where M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II}. The Zn^{II} complexes exhibit exothermic peak in the temperature range 430–590° and the corresponding mass-loss curve in the thermograms accounting to the loss of ligand. The residue left after the decomposition of organic moiety accounts to that of ZnO⁹.

The characteristic IR absorptions of the ligands CPOA and CPMA and their assignments are given in the Experimental section. The ν_{N-H} ligand bands shift to low frequency side by 50–140 cm⁻¹ indicating the coordination of

amide NH group¹⁰ to the metal ions. The disappearance of ν_{COOH} absorptions confirms that the deprotonation takes place on coordination. This is further confirmed by the appearance of new absorptions around 1500 and 1390 cm^{-1} characteristic of coordinated carboxylate anion group, i.e., $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$, respectively¹¹. In case of the Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} complexes, the broad absorptions at 3350–2700 cm^{-1} are attributed to water molecules. An absorption at 820 cm^{-1} in the case of the Fe^{III} complexes confirms that the water molecules are coordinated¹². The Zn^{II} complexes show no absorption in this region indicating that the water molecules are not coordinated. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band of amide group shifted to high frequency side by 10–25 cm^{-1} confirming that the amide carbonyl oxygen is not coordinated to the metal ion⁴. These changes in the IR spectra of the complexes indicate that ligands CPOA and CPMA act as quadridentate ligands coordinating through two amide nitrogen atoms and two carboxylate oxygen atoms. The amide-II absorption is shifted to low frequency side by 20–40 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes, confirming the coordination of amide nitrogen atom⁴. In addition, all the complexes exhibit $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ absorptions at 380–420 and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ absorptions at 355–375 cm^{-1} in the far-IR region¹³.

The magnetic moments of all the complexes obtained from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities¹⁴ are presented in Table 1. The magnetic moments of the Fe^{III} complexes indicate them to be low-spin complexes¹⁵ with significant orbital contribution¹⁶. The low values of the Co^{II} complexes also indicate them to be low-spin complexes. The Ni^{II} complexes are found to be diamagnetic. The magnetic moment values of the Cu^{II} complexes are close to the single electron moments of several Cu^{II} complexes. The magnetic property studies indicate that the ligands CPOA and CPMA are strong field producing ligands as evident from similar N, O⁻ donor ligands¹⁷. The Zn^{II} (d^{10}) complexes exhibit very low magnetic susceptibilities and hence are diamagnetic.

The low-spin Fe^{III} complexes exhibit absorptions at 29410, 25640 cm^{-1} (CPOA) and 30770, 25905 and 23530 cm^{-1} (CPMA). The low-spin Fe^{III} complexes are reported¹⁸ to absorb radiation corresponding to ${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, ${}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2T_{2g}$, ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transitions. However, all these four transitions are not intense and may not be observed generally. Hence, the absorptions are assignable to the above transitions.

The low-spin Co^{II} complexes of CPOA and CPMA exhibit four to six absorptions in the electronic spectral region. Urbach *et al.*¹⁹ calculated single electron d -orbital energies for $\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{-Co}^{\text{II}}$ square-planar chelates and proposed

that a total of nine transitions are possible. Thus, the transitions observed in the region 16395–28750 cm^{-1} indicate that the Co^{II} complexes of CPOA and CPMA have square-planar geometry. The electronic spectra of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} , d^8 complexes exhibit absorptions at 15835, 21835 and 24690 cm^{-1} [$\text{Ni}(\text{CPOA})$] and 16015, 21980 and 24785 cm^{-1} [$\text{Ni}(\text{CPMA})$], assignable to ${}^1A_2 \leftarrow {}^1A_1(\nu_1)$, ${}^1B_2 \leftarrow {}^1A_1(\nu_2)$, ${}^1E \leftarrow {}^1A_1(\nu_3)$ transitions of Ni^{II} in square planar environment, D_{2d} point group.

The analytical and thermal studies indicate that the Cu^{II} ion is coordinated to quadridentate ligands. The Cu^{II} , d^9 system with only one unpaired electron forms four-coordinate (i) tetrahedral complexes ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \approx 2.2$ B.M.) and (ii) square-planar complexes ($\mu_{\text{eff}} \approx 1.8$ B.M.). The lower magnetic moment values (Table 1) and the electronic spectral absorption in the higher energy region at 15760 [$\text{Cu}(\text{CPOA})$] and 15875 cm^{-1} [$\text{Cu}(\text{CPMA})$] as against the low energy (<10000 cm^{-1}) absorptions for tetrahedral complexes²⁰ confirm that the Cu^{II} complexes of CPOA and CPMA have square-planar geometry.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra (DMSO-d_6) of diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes have been recorded in DMSO-d_6 . The conspicuous feature of these spectra as compared to those of the ligands is the absence of the signal at the down field (11.5 ppm) of the COOH group. This confirms the deprotonation. The broad signal of NH proton shifted to low field side (from 8.2 to ~ 9.0 ppm) in the spectra of the complexes indicating the coordination of amide nitrogen. The other proton signals bonded to carbon atoms (aromatic and aliphatic) did not show any shift. The spectra of the Zn^{II} complexes exhibit a new signal at 3.64 ppm characteristic of the protons of water molecules. In the Ni^{II} complexes, no signal was observed in this region confirming the absence of water molecules.

The ESR spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes recorded at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature were found to be anisotropic with only two peaks. From the spectra of the respective complexes the parameters like g_{\parallel} (2.26), g_{\perp} (2.06), g_{av} (2.14) and G (4.35) have been obtained. Because of the poor resolution of the spectra even at the liquid nitrogen temperature, the A_{\parallel} and A_{\perp} values could not be obtained. The spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) values have been evaluated using the equation, $g_{\parallel} = 2.0023 - 8\lambda/\Delta E$, and were found to be 507 and 511, respectively, for [$\text{Cu}(\text{CPOA})$] and [$\text{Cu}(\text{CPMA})$]. The lower values of λ as compared to the free-ion value indicate that there is a considerable mixing of ground and excited state terms. The higher magnetic moment values (1.85 B.M.) evaluated

from the ESR spectra and the experimentally determined values confirm the same.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Anthranilic acid was recrystallized and the solvents were purified by distillation before use. The C, H and N were analysed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 instrument. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker WP80SY instrument at Institut für Anorganische und Analytische Chemie, Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany. Conductance was recorded on a Digisun DI-909 conductometer. Infrared and electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 283 and Shimadzu UV-VIS 160 spectrophotometers, respectively. ESR spectra were recorded at room temperature and liquid nitrogen temperature on JEOL-JES-PE-3X and Varian ESR spectrometers, respectively, at R.S.I.C., I.I.T., Madras. Thermograms were recorded on a Mettler-TA-2000C instrument.

Preparation of ligands : To anthranilic acid (10 g) dissolved in dry benzene (50 ml) was added oxalyl chloride (3.2 ml)/malonyl chloride (3.5 ml) dropwise during 30 min with stirring while cooling in the salt-ice mixture. The light yellow solids separated were washed with dry benzene, dried in air and crystallized from methanol in presence of activated charcoal to yield the products : CPOA (7.1 g, 75%), m.p. 182° (Found : C, 58.32; H, 3.36; N, 8.48. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$ calcd. for : C, 58.53; H, 3.68; N, 8.53%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3480, 3400 (NH), 2850, 2660, 2570 (COOH), 1675, 1620 (C=O), 1550 (amide-II), δ (DMSO- d_6) 11.58 (2H, s, COOH), 8.18 (2H, br, NH), 7.48–7.72 (8H, m, ArH); CPMA (6.2 g, 60%), m.p. 167° (Found : C, 58.43; H, 4.65; N, 7.97. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$ calcd. for : C, 58.77; H, 4.89; N, 8.18%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3480, 3400 (NH), 2850, 2660, 2570 (COOH), 1675, 1630 (C=O), 1580 (amide-II), δ (DMSO- d_6) 11.50 (2H, s, COOH), 8.20 (2H, br, NH), 7.48–7.72 (8H, m, ArH), 3.28 (2H, s, OCCH_2CO).

Preparation of complexes : To CPOA (1.6 mmol) or CPMA (1.6 mmol) dissolved in methanol (30 ml) was added the hydrated metal salt FeCl_3 , Co(OAc)_2 , Ni(OAc)_2 , Cu(OAc)_2 or Zn(OAc)_2 (1.6 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) slowly with stirring. The mixture was refluxed on a hot water-bath for 3–5 h. The resulting solid complexes were washed with cold methanol and dried over fused CaCl_2 (yields 61–80%).

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